

**GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION
INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES**

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INTRODUCTION

Based on the decisions, decrees and speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the introduction of information, communication and modern pedagogical technologies into the educational system, today's advanced pedagogical technologies, information base resources and the increase in the need for software means that the issue of its production and use in education is urgent. This article " Republic study monitoring centers _ going mobile app platform " _ Create topic based on prepared . Mobile app platform from creating the goal school from the lessons except addition study from training in use convenience Create . Him addition study to training to attend at will has been to users present reach for intended . This is it the platform in creating mobile app creator programs and from him use stages and about data given _ As a result of the transition of the higher education system of our country to the credit-module system, great changes have been made in this system. Decree No. PF-5953 dated March 2, 2020 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions " 2020/2021 academic year It is said that the procedure for gradually transferring the educational process to the credit-module system should be introduced in higher educational institutions of the republic starting from 2016.

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Today's Android operating system per day system mobile devices in the field the most wide spread _ Android is open resourceful code and Google Policy because of own products for mobile device work manufacturers of the android platform free of charge to use possibility giving popularity increased . Android is used because Samsung, HTC, Sony, Huawei big mobile devices is used .

Initially , Google is famous android versions of robots to give for expanded went , but authorship the right problems because of this to the idea have refused to be . of the system each one version , from version 1.5 starting

with sweets on the subject own the code takes _ Code signs Latin of the alphabet alphabet in order is determined .

In fields related to programming, this term is used a lot. The abbreviation API is derived from the initials of the words Application Programming Interface, which is translated as the program programming interface or program software interface.

WWW can be thought of as a large network of interconnected servers, where each page is stored. It is also possible to turn an ordinary laptop into a server, which ensures the operation of an entire site on the network. Local servers can act as temporary servers for developers to create sites. When `www.facebook.com` is written in the address bar of the browser, the necessary request is sent to the facebook server in another location. As soon as the browser receives a response from the server, it interprets ("draws") the code and displays the page to the user.

The browser waits for the response in the HTML markup language to generate the entire web page. And the Google Calendar API returns data in JSON or XML format.

If a request to the API is sent by the company's website server, the company's server is the client (just as the browser is the client when the user visits the site).

With the help of API, the user will be able to perform various actions without leaving the site.

Currently, most sites use multiple API services. Many tasks have ready-made solutions, in which case they offer libraries or other services to programmers. Many developers distribute parts of the application to multiple servers during the development process. These parts communicate with each other using APIs. Programs that provide additional or auxiliary functions to the main server are called microservices.

So, when a company provides an API to its users, it means that the company has created a bunch of custom URLs, which in turn only return data.

The programmer working in the front-end part sends the necessary parameters to these APIs, specifying the type of the method. This request comes to the server where the program is running through internet traffic and performs its work through the methods of the Controller or RestController class that we have created and returns a value from the database. The returned response is displayed to the user in the UI section. This is the principle of operation of web applications.

Java technology is a very simple, highly secure, powerful, fully object-oriented programming language that is platform-independent. With it, you can write programs even for the smallest devices. Java technology is completely based on Java's syntax, C++. Therefore, those who know C++ can easily learn Java. But most of its features have been removed. For example: Direct work with pointers, that is, there is no concept of a separate pointer in Java. Reloading operators has also been removed. More importantly, unused memory (unreferenced objects) is automatically cleaned. This is done by Garbage Collector (GC) in Java.

The term "database" has several terms. They are not opposites, but different points of view on the same concept. Let's live in one of them:

Database - a set of data stored in computer memory and in the form of a data set that defines the general principles of their description, storage and manipulation.

The information model understands the information about the object selected and structured according to this purpose.

Modern database servers include all kinds of changes and mechanisms for high-level interaction with the user. These development tools allow users to create applications that function as DBBMS.

ZBBMS is a software package that many people use to maintain these programs and use the results of their work.

Software includes all computer programs used to operate a database management system. Three types of software are required to perform all DBMS functions: 1) system software (controls all hardware components and provides access to all other programs running on the computer);

SQL capabilities. SQL(Structured Query Language) – This query language consists of many operators through which users and programs can access the database in Oracle(MBBT). Oracle utilities or various programs can perform database access without SQL operators, but it is impossible not to use this query language when executing queries.

In June 1970, EF Codd made his paper EF Codd, "A Relational Model of Data for Large Shared Data Banks" public. This article was published in Communications of the ACM. Nowadays, this model of Codd is accepted as the final model of "relational database management system (RMBBT)". IBM developed the SEQUEL (Structured English Query Language) language to implement Codd's model. This language was later changed to SQL, but is still referred to as a "sequel". 1979 Relational Software (now Oracle) Corporation

released the first commercial development of SQL. Currently, SQL is the standard language of RMBBT.

The SQL language works in query-result form. Queries are issued not for each element, but for a whole group, and the result is obtained. For SQL, it doesn't matter what form or order the data in the database is, users

does not need to know the data. Only by writing the operators correctly will it be possible to extract the desired data.

SQL is the common standard language for all database management systems. It follows that if you learn this language once, you can work with any MBBT. A set of sql operators (small query program) created in one MBBT can be moved to any MBBT.

The following tasks can be performed using SQL statements:

- Obtaining data by request.
- Adding data to the rows of the table, deleting and updating the rows.
- Create, modify and delete objects.
- Set database and object permissions.
- Create database users and ensure database security.

There are 2 types of SQL: interactive and built-in. These 2 types of SQL work the same but are used in different places.

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